

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№10

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025 oktyabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 – Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 – Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 762 sahifa.
2025-yil, 30-oktyabr,

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

JAHON MOLIYA TIZIMIDA “YASHIL” MOLIYALASHTIRISHNI RIVOJLANISHINING MUAMMOLARI VA SHARTLARI	12
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
EKOLOGIK MIGRANTSIYANI MINTAQAVIY MIQYOSDA MUVOFIQLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI	18
Bahtiyor Ismoilov Ulug‘bek o‘g‘li, Kadirova Zulayxo Abduxalimovna	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BANK XIZMATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH HOLATI	25
Davletova Nilufar Tulanovna	
EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA MINTAQANI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	30
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI	37
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
MAHALLIY XOMASHYO BAZASIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISH YO‘LLARI	46
Sultanov Dilshod Normamatovich	
IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLARDA INSON KAPITALIGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB QILISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	50
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
O‘QITUVCHILAR VA TALABALAR UCHUN INNOVATSION TA‘LIM DASTURLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISHDA XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHUV MEXANIZMLARI	62
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA‘RIDAN FOYDALANGANLIK UCHUN SOLIQLARNING ILMIY-TADQIQOTLAR SHARHI	68
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o‘g‘li	
RESPUBLIKA IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTIDA OLIY TA‘LIMNI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH VA INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINING O‘RNI	74
Jonuzokov Mirzabek Kulmamatovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	80
O. Nurmuradov	
ICHKI AUDIT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA BUXGALTERIYA MA‘LUMOTLARINING ICHKI AUDIT JARAYONIDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	85
Xamidov Javoxir Shavkat o‘g‘li, Muxitdinov Shoxijaxon Xudoyor o‘g‘li	
XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNING MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZMLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	90
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
KORPORATIV TUZILMALARDA INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISHDAGI ROLI	95
Qurbonov Javlonbek Jurabekovich, Raxmatov Faxriddin Xasanovich	
GLOBAL RIVOJLANISH JARAYONIDA SUG‘URTA XIZMATLARINI ISLOH QILISH MASALALARI	99
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o‘g‘li	

DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	103
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA ERISHISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO'LLASH METODOLOGIYASINING AHAMIYATI	109
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ КАК ФАКТОР КОНКУРЕНТНОГО ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА.....	115
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURSLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISHGA OID TADQIQOTLARNING NAZARIY TAHLILI.....	123
NasimdjanoV Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINI MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH: XULQ-ATVOR IQTISODIYOTI VA PROGRESSIV TARIFLARNI LOYIHALASH	129
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
DAVLAT RAQAMLI LOYIHALARI: UZINFOCOMNING TA'LIM TIZIMI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKKA QO'SHGAN HISSASI	134
Raxmatxo'jayev Axrorxo'ja Akmal o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ПАСПОРТОВ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ.....	140
Мансурова Сайёра Бахтияровна	
BANK XIZMATLARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	148
Xolikova Oydin Olimjonovna	
PNEVMOMEXANIK YIGIRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI XUSUSIYATLARI	153
Jumaniyazov Kadam, Salimov Shuhrat Halimovich, Nazarov Ramazon Anvarovich	
GREEN INDUSTRY AND THE ECONOMY OF ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY CONSTRUCTION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND UZBEKISTAN'S OPPORTUNITIES.....	158
Mansurova Sayyora Bakhtiyor kizi	
TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAHLILI	166
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING MIKRO VA MAKRO TUZILMALARI, ULARNING FUNKSIONAL METADOLOGIK TAMOYILLARI.....	171
Z.Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT ULUSHI MAVJUD KORXONALARNI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBADAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	176
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
MAHSULOT TANNARXINI ANIQLASHDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARJATLARINI OG'ISHISHLARI VA ULARNI TAQSIMLASH	183
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СТОИМОСТИ СПОРТИВНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ И ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ АУТСОРСИНГА	186
Исмагулова Гульмира Нуралиевна	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYASI.....	193
Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA XIZMATLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TASHKILYIY MEXANIZMLARI.....	198
Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLARNI JALB QILISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA.....	203
Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmat o'g'li	

MEHNATGA LAYOQATLI TRANSPORT SOHASIDAGI AHOLINI ISH O'RINLARI BILAN TA'MINLANGANLIK HOLATINI TAHLILI	207
Abdullayeva Nigora Shamsiddinovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK SOHASINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI	212
Mdraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI DIVERSIFIKATSIIYASI VA GAROV TA'MINOTI SIFATINING BANK BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	220
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYASI DOIRASIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	226
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XIZMATLARNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KLASTERLI MEXANIZMI TAHLILI	232
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o'g'li	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TUZILMALARIDA MOLIYAVIY MUNOSABATLARNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	236
Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich	
XALQARO SAVDONING RIVOJLANISHI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI	242
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING YANGI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHGA QARATILGAN NAZARIY JIHATLAR	247
Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA BOJXONA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	254
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
DAVLAT TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI YURITISH	262
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdugarimovich	
РАЗРАБОТКА ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ КРЕАТИВНЫХ ИНДУСТРИЙ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКУЮ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН	273
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
A NEW STAGE IN THE APPLICATION OF MARKET MECHANISMS TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	285
Ibrayim Maxkamov	
RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH ORQALI SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI	291
Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIDA DXSH ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING SHAKLLANISHI	297
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH	301
Shaymanov To'liqin Mahmayusupovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЦИФРОВЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В НАЛОГОВОМ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ	306
Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
СИНТЕЗ НЕЧЕТКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕПЛОЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	311
Бахриева Хуршида Аскарходжаевна, Сафаров Шохрух Шарофович, Бахрамов Муҳаммадали Ералиевичасистент	
ШАНХАЙСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА КАК КАТАЛИЗАТОР ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕЛЕЙ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	319
Базарова Гулнара Гуламовна	

O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARINING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA BANK KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	323
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QUESTIONS ABOUT THE STUDY OF PERFORMANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF APPLICATION OF LOADING AND EXTRACTING EQUIPMENT	327
Azamat Umirzokov	
MATOLARNING HAVO O'TKAZUVCHANLIGI KORRELATSION TAHLILI.....	334
Ismailov Nurulla Tuychibayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASHNING AFZALLIKLARI	339
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
IKKI QATLAMLI ARALASH TOLA TARKIBLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMASINI OLIISH USULI	343
Usnatdinova Elmira Faxratdinovna, Mirusmanov Baxtiyor, Abdurahimova Fazilat Abdullayevna	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYATI ORGANLARIDA ENG ILG'OR TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARINING OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	347
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS ON THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN: CROSS-SECTORAL ANALYSIS.....	354
Jumayeva Kamola Azimjonovna, Khasanova Iroda Azizbek kizi	
KORXONA INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY MASALALARI XUSUSIDA	362
Ilyasova Barno Axmadovna	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI O'ZLASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	371
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH ASOSIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	378
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASHDA EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	385
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY KONSEPTUAL MEKANIZMLARI.....	392
Jalolov Abbasxon Ravshanxon o'g'li	
TEPKI UZELI KONSTRUKTIV XOSSALARI TAHLILI	398
Bozorova Farida Maxmudjonovna	
НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ ОБЪЕДИНЕНИЯ АКЦИЗНОГО НАЛОГА НА НЕФТЕПРОДУКТЫ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	405
Пулатов Дилшод Хақбердиевич, Маматкулов Салимжон Рахмонкулович, Хужамурадов Аброрбек Рўзимурат ўғли, Воронин Сергей Александрович, Абдиев Мансур Мусурмонович	
OLIY TA'LIMGA INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATI: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR	410
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE NETWORK.....	416
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTON INVESTITSION MUHIT VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	421
Tirkashev Farruxjon Xolyigitovich	
МНОГОМЕРНАЯ БЕДНОСТЬ И УСТОЙЧИВОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ОЦЕНКА ЧЕРЕЗ РАМКУ МРІ	426
Мамаризоев Жахонгир Исохонович	
ОЦЕНКА И ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ВЛИЯНИЯ МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ НА ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБМЕННОГО КУРСА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	430
Норбаева Мухлиса Акрам кизи	

RAQAMLI TO'LOVLAR ASOSLARI VA XAVFSIZLIGI	440
<i>Yaqubov Azizbek G'anibekovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI BOSHQARISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI	444
<i>Xomidov Xojjakbar Adxamovich</i>	
SOLIQ SIYOSATI ORQALI INKLYUZIV IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARI.....	449
<i>Saydakbarova Madinaxon Anisbekovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA STARTAP EKOTIZIMINING SHAKLLANISHI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHI YO'LLARI.....	454
<i>Suleymanova Shoira Alavxanovna</i>	
MILLIY IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING O'RNI	459
<i>Alimova Dilfuzaxon Rustam qizi</i>	
MEHNAT BOZORINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHNING MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	464
<i>Botirova Sarvinoz Bobir qizi</i>	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNI TASHKIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	469
<i>Qurboniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich</i>	
INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI MUQOBIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH USULLARINING MANBALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH YO'LLARI	474
<i>Boboqulov Akmal Muborakbekovich</i>	
RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINING MOHIYATI VA TURLARI.....	482
<i>Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich</i>	
FISKAL BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING TARTIBGA SOLISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	491
<i>Sulaymonov Farrux Shuxratovich</i>	
ИНДЕКС ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ МОНИТОРИНГА УРОВНЯ ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ.....	496
<i>Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна</i>	
BANK MAJBURIYATLARI VA AKTIVLARINING VAQTINCHALIK NOMUTANOSIBLIK LARI RISKINI KAMAYTIRISH	502
<i>Ibrohimov D.M.</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON RAQAMLI PLATFORMALARI FAOLIYATIDA RAQOBAT SIYOSATINING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	507
<i>Saparov Islom O'Imasovich</i>	
RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING YONDASHUVLARINING QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIGA TATBIQI.....	514
<i>Abdikarimova Zilola Baxramovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI KAPITALI TARKIBIDA DAROMAD MANBALARINING ULUSHI VA KAPITALLASHUV JARAYONIDAGI O'RNI	520
<i>Tursunov Mustafo Mirzayevich</i>	
AHOLINI IJTIMOY HIMOYA QILISH TIZIMIDA INSTITUSIONAL HAMKORLIKNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI TAHLILI	524
<i>Abdullayeva Sayyora Aleksandrovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	528
<i>Bobojonova Sevara Baxrombek qizi</i>	
MINTAQA SANOATI RAQAMLI XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA TIJORATLASHTIRISHNI "SMART" MODELI	533
<i>Norov Murodjon Maxmudovich</i>	

TOMORQADAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH- KAMBAG'ALLIK MUAMMOSINI YUMSHATISHNING MUHIM OMILI	539
Xamidjon Shaxobov	
SUG'URTA KORXONALARIDA REZERVLAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	544
Najimova Nigora	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XITOY BOZORINING O'RNINI	549
Mardanov Aziz Yusupovich	
THE IMPORTANCE OF GREEN ENERGY IN THE ECONOMY OF FERGANA REGION: CURRENT TRENDS AND PROBLEMS	555
Khayrullaev Zoidjon	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLARNING UNDIRILISHI BO'YICHA XORIJ TAJRIBASI	559
Mitillayev Ibrohimjon Tursunpulatovich	
RAQAMLI MOLIYAVIY XIZMATLAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	563
Muyassarzoda Fayziyeva	
MOLIYAVIY MEXANIZM SIFATIDA SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARI TO'LOVGA LAYOQATLILIGINI BELGILASHNING O'ZIGA XOS HUSUSIYATLARI	570
Abdullayev Erkinjon A'zamovich	
MAMLAKAT YAIM QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT HAJMINI STATISTIK VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL USULLARI ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	578
Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich	
XALQARO TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	585
Eshtaev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, Ivatov Irisbeg	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA AUDIT TIZIMLARINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	590
To'laganov Ziyovuddin Kamolitdin o'g'li	
JAHON SEMENT SANOATIDAGI TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	595
Abdujabbarov Abdulaziz Abdurashid o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОГО АНАЛИЗА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	600
Бекбаева Феруза Бахтиеровна	
BARQAROR MOLIYAVIY RENTABELLIK BANKLARNING DAROMADLILIGINI TA'MINLASH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	606
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	
REKLAMA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKKA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR.....	612
Xamrakulov Azamat Baxritdinovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЕМ (LMS) В ОНЛАЙН ОБРАЗОВАНИИ И ЕЕ РОЛЬ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: АНАЛИЗ И СРАВНЕНИЕ	618
Атабоева Шахризода Равшановна, Бекчанов Бекчан Юлдашевич	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ	623
Киличева Ф.Б.	
DAVLAT TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA DEBITORLAR VA KREDITORLAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	628
Sultonova Mushtariy Abdulabbosovna	
NARX BELGILASH-IQTISODIY MANFAATDORLIKNING ASOSIY OMILI VA NARXNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOIYILLARI	635
Soxadaliyev Abdurashid Mamadaliyevich	

SUTNI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDAGI ISHLAB CHIQRISH JARAYONLARINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	639
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TARIF STAVKALARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ORQALI FISKAL BARQARORLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	644
Rizayev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
IPOTEKA KREDITLASH JARAYONINING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	652
Akrom Mardiyev	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGI TAHLILI	659
Ulashbayev Shohruh Abdivaxobovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF APPLYING NEW HETEROCOMPOSITE POLYMER MATERIALS IN ENGINEERING ACTIVITIES	665
Umida Ziyamukhamedova, Mirjalol Abdulakimov	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ «МАХАЛЛАБАЙ»: ДЕЦЕНТРАЛИЗАЦИЯ И ТЕОРИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ.....	672
Қосимжонов Нозимжон Қозимжон ўғли	
EKOLOGIK AUDITNI TASHKIL ETISHDA RISKLARNI JORIY ETISH TARTIBI	676
Abdullayev Xurshidjon Nazrullo o'g'li	
CORPORATE CULTURE AND ITS ROLE IN TALENT MANAGEMENT	683
Shoyunusova Arofat, Sanjar Mirzaliev	
SIRDARYO VILOYATI SHAROITIDA BIOMASSA ASOSIDA OZUQA ISHLAB CHIQRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	687
Xazratkulov Niyoz Namazbayevich	
ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	692
Воронин Сергей Александрович, Азимова Феруза Маликовна	
ENERGETIKA LOYIHALARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHDA TO'SIQLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR	700
Tilakov Ismoiljon Usmonovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	706
O'roqov Firdavs Ortiqniyoz o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI BOZORLARNI MONOPOLIYAGA QARSHI TARTIBGA SOLISH MEKANIZMLARI VA TAKOMLLASHTIRISH TAKLIFLARI.....	710
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
JAHON SEMENT SANOATIDAGI TENDENSIYALAR VA O'ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	717
Abdujabbarov Alisher Abdullayevich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	722
Mufitillayeva Safiya Qodir qizi	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASHDA STATISTIK AXBOROT TIZIMINING O'RNI	728
Musurmonova Mahbuba Omonovna	
INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR VA ULARNING AGRAR SOHAGA TA'SIRI.....	732
Ortiqov Sulton Davronqul o'g'li	
DIRECTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING OF COSTS.....	736
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabiyevna	
БОРЬБА С ТЕНЕВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	740
Арзиев Шерзод	

REKREATSION TURIZM OBYEKTLARINING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGI: YALTA VA KISLOVODSK SANATORIYALARI MISOLIDA.....	746
Najmitdinov G'ayratbek Sharifovich	
KORXONA SAMARADORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA STRATEGIK REJALASHTIRISH MEZONLARI VA OMILLARINING O'RNI	752
Ubaydullayev Lutfulla Xabibullayevich	
ANALYSIS OF INTERACTIVE PLATFORMS THAT DEVELOP MOTIVATION	757
Maksuda Mukhammadovna Jurayeva, Zarnigor To'liqinovna Sattorova	

ANALYSIS OF INTERACTIVE PLATFORMS THAT DEVELOP MOTIVATION

Maksuda Mukhammadovna Jurayeva

Associate Professor, PhD
Department of French Philology
Bukhara State University
Email: m.m.juraeva@buxdu.uz

Zarnigor To'liqinovna Sattorova

Director of the private educational center
"AKADEMIK SCHOOL"

Abstract. This article analyzes the impact and importance of interactive platforms that develop motivation. In the modern education system, interactive platforms, such as online learning resources, mobile applications, and gamification elements, play an important role in increasing students' interest in the learning process. The article examines the main features of such platforms, their role in the educational process, and how they can effectively increase student motivation.

Keywords: motivation, interactive platforms, educational technologies, online learning resources, gamification, student interest, learning process, self-management.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada motivatsiyani rivojlantiruvchi interaktiv platformalarning ahamiyati va ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida onlayn o'quv resurslari, mobil ilovalar va gamifikatsiya elementlari kabi interaktiv platformalar talabalarning o'quv jarayoniga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Maqolada bunday platformalarning asosiy xususiyatlari, ularning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va talaba motivatsiyasini samarali oshirish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: motivatsiya, interaktiv platformalar, ta'lim texnologiyalari, onlayn o'quv resurslari, gamifikatsiya, talaba qiziqishi, o'quv jarayoni, o'zini boshqarish.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется значение и влияние интерактивных платформ, развивающих мотивацию. В современной образовательной системе интерактивные платформы, такие как онлайн-обучающие ресурсы, мобильные приложения и элементы геймификации, играют важную роль в повышении интереса студентов к учебному процессу. В статье рассматриваются основные характеристики таких платформ, их роль в образовательном процессе и способы эффективного повышения мотивации студентов.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, интерактивные платформы, образовательные технологии, онлайн-обучающие ресурсы, геймификация, интерес студентов, учебный процесс, самоуправление.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern education system, motivation plays an important role in the successful learning process of students. Student interest and active participation, in turn, help to improve the quality of education. Therefore, interactive platforms that develop motivation are widely used in the educational process. These platforms provide students with opportunities to consolidate their knowledge, acquire new skills, and develop themselves. Interactive platforms, in turn, serve to increase student motivation through gamification elements, real-time exchange of ideas, and opportunities for collaboration. These technologies not only make the learning process interesting and engaging, but also allow adaptation to the individual needs of students. Such approaches are important for introducing innovative methods in educational institutions and encouraging students to self-manage.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The introduction of digital technologies in the modern education system creates great opportunities for improving and increasing the efficiency of educational processes. Today, digital educational tools, including online platforms, distance learning systems, virtual laboratories, and mobile applications, are widely used in the educational process. These tools not only improve the quality of education, but also have a positive effect on student motivation.

Studies on the impact of digital educational tools on student motivation show that these tools are important in the educational process.

I. Kalandarov and M. Rustamova [1] studied the impact of digital educational platforms on the educational process and the quality of education in vocational educational institutions. The authors analyze the pedagogical and didactic capabilities of digital technologies and emphasize that they serve to improve students' knowledge, effectively monitor their mastery, and individualize the learning process.

B.S.Azamkhonov[2] explained the relevance of comprehensively understanding and analyzing the impact of Mixed Reality (MR) technology on students' academic performance and information literacy. He conducted a study aimed at studying the impact of MR technology in educational settings and determining its importance in improving student academic performance. Learning motivation is the activity of learners formed by their internal interest in learning and external factors. Digital tools in the educational process increase students' interest in mastering educational materials by increasing interactivity and creativity. At the same time, digital tools allow for more convenient, flexible and person-oriented organization of education. The results of the study of the impact of MR technology on students' academic performance show that the ability of digital tools to develop interactivity and creativity is important in increasing learning motivation.

At the same time, learning motivation is defined as the activity of students formed by their internal interest in learning and external motivating factors. This motivation is one of the important factors in achieving success in the educational process. Internal motivation is explained by factors such as interest in learning and the desire to develop oneself, while external motivation is associated with factors such as incentives, results or rewards. If students have high motivation in the educational process, their learning rate increases and they are actively involved in the educational process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used survey, observation, and experimental research methods to examine the impact of digital learning tools on students' motivation to learn. The main tools used for the study were online questionnaires developed using Google Forms, interactive sessions with students via the Zoom platform, Kahoot, and Quizizz.

In this study, the following research methods were used to study the impact of digital learning tools on students' learning motivation:

1. Survey: Specially designed questionnaires were distributed to study students' experience of using digital learning tools, their level of interest and motivation. This method is based on the principles of Intrinsic Motivation Measurement developed by Deci and Ryan [6].

2. Observation: Students' activities using digital tools were observed and their level of participation and interest in the learning process were analyzed. This approach was implemented based on the principles of interactive learning proposed by [7].

3. Experiment: Students were divided into two groups, one group received education using digital tools, and the other group received education using traditional methods. According to the results of the experiment, the relationship between learning motivation and results was analyzed [8].

The study involved 2nd and 3rd year students of higher education institutions in our country. The total number of respondents was 120, selected from the fields of computer science and pedagogy. The respondents were between the ages of 18 and 24, 45% of whom were women and 55% were men.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The introduction of digital technologies in the modern education system creates great opportunities for improving and increasing the efficiency of educational processes. Today, digital educational tools, including online platforms, distance learning systems, virtual laboratories, and mobile applications, are widely used in the educational process. These tools not only improve the quality of education, but also have a positive effect on student motivation.

Digital learning tools play an important role in modern education, as they optimize the learning process and increase students' interest in the learning process. At the same time, it is necessary to enrich pedagogical approaches for the effective implementation of technologies.

The results of the study showed that digital learning tools are an effective tool for increasing students' motivation to learn. The fact that the level of motivation in the experimental group increased by 25%, and students rated digital lessons as interesting and understandable, confirms the positive impact of these tools on the learning process. However, there are also problems, such as adaptation to technical infrastructure and platforms, which can be further improved by eliminating them.

Based on the results, it was observed that the motivation of students who were taught using digital tools increased significantly. This change was found to be associated with increasing interactivity in the learning process, expanding the possibilities of personalized learning, and increasing the effectiveness of learning through visualization of knowledge. In the study, students in the group that used digital tools showed high activity in freely expressing their thoughts, self-assessment, and independent problem solving. These observations are consistent with foreign studies, for example, in the study conducted by Clark and Mayer (2016), [5] it was noted that digital learning tools and multimedia technologies have a positive effect on student motivation.

Clark and Mayer's work shows that the use of digital learning tools stimulates the activity of students by individualizing the learning process and deepening understanding. In particular, lessons enriched with multimedia elements present the educational material in a more interesting and understandable form. This significantly increases students' interest in learning activities.

Also, in the studies conducted in Uzbekistan by Abdukahhorov (2023), [9] it was noted that the motivation of students who received education using digital tools increased and this process had a positive impact on educational effectiveness. In particular, it was found that students were satisfied with the opportunity to independently manage their time, perform practical exercises through digital platforms, and assess their mastery.

An analysis of foreign and domestic studies shows that digital educational tools are one of the important factors activating the educational process, which encourages students to take a responsible approach to their activities. These tools are also important not only in increasing learning motivation, but also in developing creative thinking, critical thinking, and collaborative work skills.

During the study, it was observed that students who received education using digital tools showed high motivation and activity in relation to their learning processes. It was found that the level of motivation among students participating in the experimental group increased by 25%. This is due to the fact that digital learning tools present learning materials in an understandable and interesting way, as well as increasing the opportunity for independent learning.

Similar conclusions have been drawn in foreign studies. For example, Clark and Mayer (2016) noted in their work that learning motivation with digital tools increases significantly, as multimedia technologies make it easier for students to understand the materials. Also, research by Jonassen (2004) showed that interactive lessons are an important factor in developing students' creative and critical thinking skills.

After the experiment, students expressed their opinion that the materials explained through digital tools were more interesting and understandable. This data supports the theory of "Primary Learning Principles" developed by Merrill (2002).

Overall, the results of the study confirmed that there is an opportunity to increase learning motivation and activity using digital tools. At the same time, it was identified that measures should be taken to eliminate technical problems and adapt students to technology. The results of foreign and domestic studies are consistent with each other and indicate the need for an integrated approach to ensure the effective use of digital educational tools.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above research and analysis, it can be said that digital educational tools have become an integral part of the modern education system, which not only increases the efficiency of the learning process, but also significantly increases student motivation. Interactive, visual and person-oriented approaches arouse

students' intrinsic interest in learning, improve the level of mastery and encourage independent learning. In the future, the effective integration of digital educational tools into the educational process and their harmonization with pedagogical approaches will serve to bring the quality of education to a new level.

List of used literature:

1. Kalandarov, I. I., & Rustamova, M. A. (2024). Muassasalarida raqamli ta'lim platformalarining ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri. *Мир исследований*, 1(1), 45–52.
2. Azamxonov, B. S. (2024). Talabalarining raqamli ta'lim resurslari asosida takomillashtirilgan axborot kompetentligining ko'rsatkichlari tahlili. *Research and Innovation*, 2(3), 78–85.
3. Yuldashev, E. S. (2024). Maktab o'quvchilarining o'quv faoliyati uchun ijobiy barqaror motivatsiyasini shakllantirish. *CyberLeninka*, 5(3), 123–129.
4. Okilova, K. (2023). O'qituvchini harakatlantiruvchi ichki va tashqi motivatsiya. *Jainkwell Publishing Conferences*, 4(2), 45–53.
5. Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2016). *E-Learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning* (4th ed.). Wiley.
6. Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
7. Jonassen, D. H. (2004). *Learning to Solve Problems: An Instructional Design Guide*. Pfeiffer.
8. Merrill, M. D. (2002). *First Principles of Instruction*. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 50(3), 43-59.
9. Abduqahhorov, A. (2023). Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari: Talabalar motivatsiyasi va natijadorlikka ta'siri. *O'zbekiston ta'lim jurnali*, 27(3), 56-68.
10. Mukhammadovna, Jurayeva Maksuda. “Media relations in french discourse.” *MIDDLE EUROPEAN SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN ISSN* (2021): 2694-9970.
11. Maqsuda, Jurayeva. “Yozma matbuot diskursining funktsional xususiyatlari.” *Ilm sarchashmalari* 6 (2021).
12. Muhammadovna, J. R. M. (2023, October). *GAZETA SARLAVHALARINUNG PRAGMATIK IMKONIYATINI IFODALOVCHI LINGVISTIK BELGILAR* (fransuz gazetalari misolida). In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES WITH HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS* (Vol. 1, No. 05.10, pp. 402-406).
13. Жураева, М. (2023). *ГАЗЕТА ВА УНИНГ САРЛАВХАЛАРИДАГИ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАР*. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(7), 87-95.

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100